

Analysis of the Evolution of English Military Terminology During World War Two Through Corpus Linguistics

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Abstract: The evolution of military terminology during World War Two represented a profound transformation in the language of warfare, reflecting not only advancements in technology, weaponry and strategy, but also the complex dynamics of international conflict. This study delves into the intricate process of terminological standardization and evolution, elucidating its significance in facilitating communication, enhancing operational efficiency and preserving historical knowledge within the military domain. Besides, we also focus at identifying differences between British and U.S. terminologies, the evolution of military language, management of neologisms and the usage of foreign terms in English. Utilizing a corpus of texts from the U.S. War Department and the U.S. Military Intelligence Service – written during that time frame–, as well as wartime and post-war glossaries, online dictionaries and encyclopaedias, this research compiles and analyzes terminological items to elucidate patterns of standardization, synonymy and linguistic variation within military discourse. Through a comprehensive analysis of terminological records and linguistic patterns, this research seeks to shed light on the nuanced complexities of military discourse during this pivotal period, highlighting the interplay between linguistic innovation, cultural influence and strategic imperatives.

Keywords: corpus linguistics, language of specialty, military terminology, terminology evolution analysis, World War Two

Resumen: La evolución de la terminología militar durante la Segunda Guerra Mundial representó una profunda transformación del lenguaje bélico, reflejo no sólo de los avances en tecnología, armamento y estrategia, sino también de la compleja dinámica de los conflictos internacionales. Este estudio profundiza en el intrincado proceso de normalización y evolución terminológica, dilucidando su importancia para facilitar la comunicación, mejorar la eficacia operativa y preservar el conocimiento histórico en el ámbito militar. Además, también nos centramos en identificar las diferencias entre las terminologías británica y estadounidense, la evolución del lenguaje militar, la gestión de los neologismos y el uso de términos extranjeros en inglés. Utilizando un corpus de textos del Departamento de Guerra y del Servicio de Inteligencia Militar de Estados Unidos -escritos durante ese periodo-, así como glosarios de guerra y posguerra, diccionarios en línea y enciclopedias, esta investigación recopila y analiza elementos terminológicos para dilucidar patrones de estandarización, sinonimia y variación lingüística dentro del discurso militar. A través de un análisis exhaustivo de los registros terminológicos y los patrones lingüísticos, esta investigación pretende arrojar luz sobre las complejidades matizadas del discurso militar durante este período crucial, destacando la interacción entre la innovación lingüística, la influencia cultural y los imperativos estratégicos.

Palabras clave: lingüística de corpus, lenguaje de especialidad, terminología militar, análisis de la evolución terminológica, Mundo

Index

1. Introduction

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. Terminology

2.2. Analysis of specialized language

2.3. Corpus linguistics

2.3.1 Corpora

3. Objectives and methodology

3.1 Building up a corpus

3.2 Term extraction

4. Analysis of the results

5. Conclusions

6. Bibliography

1. Introduction

The study of military terminology has been left aside for different reasons. However, this discipline started to suffer a dramatic change last century that continues today. The evolution of tactics, strategy, doctrine, weapons, equipment, uniforms, etc., implied the creation of new terminological items to describe these new conceptuological units. Besides, some old terminological items evolved to broaden their meaning or, simply, gave birth to new ones to describe more intricated conceptuological units. On the other hand, many of these terminological items finally became lexical ones. This is the language modification that occurs when typical expressions or terms from different scientific disciplines are understood and widely used by the general public during their daily interactions (Adamo, 2000, p. 86) and termed as *de-terminologization* by Meyer & Mackinstosh, (2000).

In this research, our aim was focused on the use of military terminology which was mainly written in American English language variation during World War Two. During that period of time, the U.S. Army published two glossaries of military terms. The first one showed the differences and similarities between the terminological units employed in the U.S. and the British Armies (War Department, 1943); the second one was focused mainly on normalizing those used in the United States Armed Forces. This glossary was intended to “assist in reaching a more nearly common understanding of the meaning of military terms” and was designed “specifically for the men who are writing or revising training literature” (War Department, 1944, p. iii).

The aim of terminology is to standardize the use of terminological units and the publication of glossaries helped to carry out that task. Likewise, terminology is interested in the formal organization of the complex relationship between concepts and terms (Sager, 1990, p. 2). For that reason —and in order to verify their use— our aim was focused on studying texts written during the period of time subjected to study, and whether to confirm or not that the terminological units used in these periodicals were the same ones that were included in the World War Two glossaries. It is beyond doubt that terminological units —at least, some of them— evolve over time, as well as their designations (Temmerman, 2000, p. 15), and that their univocity is not always assured (Cabré, 2000). For that reason, one of our objectives has been to confirm the evolution of terminological units and the apparition of new ones; those expressed in the English language or in the language they were conceived. Many barbarisms adopted in the English language have not been translated and some of them are no longer considered terminological units, becoming lexical ones and included in post-war English dictionaries.

Another aspect we wanted to consider was the important aid corpus linguistics makes to the study of terminology and the language of specialty. Corpus linguistics helps terminology management by using electronic corpora to identify and analyze terms, providing evidence for their usage and assisting in the compilation, description, processing, and presentation of terms (Susi et al., 2018). For that reason, we have used a corpus analysis tool —as well as a terminological one— to discover and analyze terminological units. Using either a raw corpus or a grammatically tagged one, the corpus analysis tools are an invaluable help to identify and study terminology, giving us textual contexts where we were able to analyze and describe their correct meaning and use.

In the first phase of our examination, we employed a terminological tool to extract terms from our corpus. Later on, our file of term candidates was enlarged thanks to the analysis of the same corpus by means of a corpus linguistics tool. The latter has been key to identify term candidates unknown to us and finding their definitions in the texts subjected to study. The results have been highly satisfactory: Apart from confirming that the evolution of military terminology in times of war is a fact to take seriously into account, soldiers used synonyms profusely—both, formal and colloquial ones. Finally, we have to point out that in historical terminological research—no matter whether it is a synchronic or a diachronic one—the role of the linguist is crucial. New technologies make our task more efficient but, without the human factor, no real and solid results can be attained. This idea was initially carried out in our Ph.D. thesis. However, we enlarged our corpus ten times as the previous one in order to ensure the effectiveness of our enquiry.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. Terminology

In ancient times, terminology was associated with the medieval concept of the trivium, or the set of the three liberal arts of eloquence—grammar, rhetoric and dialectic—, which is why it is now considered a purely interdisciplinary methodology (Adamo, 2000, p. 88). Today, we can assert that terminology is the study and work of compiling, describing, processing and representing terms belonging to various specialized areas in one or more languages. It differs from lexicography in the nature of the data under study, in the methodology employed and in the specialization required for such work (Sager, 1990, p. 3). On the other hand, Wüster (as cited in Cabré, 1999, p. 232) described terminology as a subject at the intersection of linguistics, cognitive science, information science, communication and computer science.

Terminology studies concepts with the primary objective of representing them within the lexicon of a language for special purposes or LSP. Wüster asserted that it was impossible to normalize terms successfully without organising all relevant concepts previously or simultaneously (1955, p. 7). For that reason, it is necessary to propose initially a knowledge model that allows describing, relating and classifying concepts. On the other hand, the terminological unit is conceived as the symbol representing a conceptual one. Therefore, concepts must be created or exist before terms are formed for their representation. We can define a concept as "the application of a process of human cognition that motivates the classification of an object through systematic or arbitrary abstraction" (Sager, 1990, p. 23). Terminology must be effective and devoid of ambiguity, aiming for monosemy and univocality. However, intentional ambiguity exists in some specialized fields (Sageder, 2010, p. 125), which plays an important role in certain disciplines, such as law (Chovanec, 2005, p. 9).

2.2. Analysis of specialized language

It is more instructive to describe specialized language by comparing it with everyday language. Language for general purposes—LGP—is used when discussing customary facts. In contrast, language for special purposes—LSP—is used to address various fields of knowledge (Bowker & Pearson, 2002, p. 25). Both types of language exist in all languages. A native speaker uses LGP in

their daily life thanks to their knowledge of grammar and vocabulary, allowing them to formulate understandable sentences for listeners and, at the same time, understand their interlocutors. However, to delve into a specific topic in greater depth, it is necessary to employ the corresponding LSP.

An LSP contains a multitude of specialized terms that, when used with common language words, form specialized discourse (Cabr, 1999, p. 25). Specialized vocabulary is one of the defining factors of LSPs and corpora are invaluable for their study. Nowadays, carrying out terminological activities without the assistance of computer tools and corpora is inconceivable (Vargas, 2012, p. 77). Corpus analysis tools are highly effective in studying specialized language, as they can display a list of words sorted alphabetically or by frequency, showing their repetition frequency (Baker et al., 2006, p. 76). Once these potential –candidate– terms are identified, they are examined in context using concordance, a process that allows us to understand their usage and meaning. Thanks to the assistance of new technologies, the terminological compilation process is currently carried out semi-automatically, with the primary aim of sharing information and achieving harmonization in terms of procedures and techniques (Sager, 1990, pp. 130-37).

Drawing upon these foundational principles, this research seeks to unravel the complexities of military terminology evolution and its enduring impact on strategic thought and operational practice.

2.3. Corpus linguistics

The emergence of corpus linguistics as a methodological tool has revolutionized the study of terminology, providing researchers with invaluable insights into the usage, evolution and contextual nuances of specialized language. By leveraging corpus analysis tools, researchers can extract and analyze terminological units within their authentic textual contexts, offering a more nuanced understanding of their usage and semantic nuances.

While corpus linguistics as a distinct field is relatively recent, its practice is as old as linguistic research itself. Historical linguistics has always been grounded in corpus analysis. According to Johansson (1995, p. 22), the most relevant evidence of language change and evolution is found in textual collections compiled across different places and time periods. The initial stage of corpus linguistics emerged prior to the dissemination of Noam Chomsky's ideas (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, p. 25). Although during that era the methodological focus with greater vigour was on language usage observation, corpus linguistics was also employed by numerous linguists, such as Boas (1940). Most proponents of the structuralist approach applied a methodology that can be defined as corpus-based. Since certain topics could not be studied through introspection, corpora continued to be utilized as a methodology, albeit minority, during the 1960s and 1970s. A corpus serves as a reliable source of frequency-based data, thus providing a much more systematic approach to linguistic analysis, subject to objective verification of its results (Leech, 1992, p. 105). However, some of the criticisms against the use of corpus linguistics were valid and prompted a reshaping of its current approach, which has ceased to be a pseudo-method (Abercrombie, 1965, p. 115) thanks to computing, evolving into a wholly viable methodology (McEnery & Wilson, 1996, p. 17).

Leech (1992, p. 107) advocated for the use of corpus linguistics, highlighting its most prominent features: its focus on linguistic activity rather than competence, its interest in linguistic description over linguistic universal principles, its orientation towards both qualitative and quantitative language models and its pursuit of a more empirical –rather than rational– vision of scientific research. Similarly, Firth (1957, p. 32) argued that the social context and purpose of communication are paramount factors to consider when studying language. His support for corpus linguistics is rooted in his assertion that authenticated language, properly recorded, should be the linguist's focal point. His methodology would be further developed by others, including Sinclair, as well as by Halliday and Hoey (McEnery & Wilson, 1996, p. 12).

In contemporary discourse, the conception of corpus linguistics is debated between its status as a theory or methodology. It is argued that corpus linguistics is not a specific research field but rather a methodological framework through which language is studied. Building upon this premise, Leech (2013, p. 8) regards a corpus –together with its corresponding software– as a tool capable of processing and analyzing vast and intricate linguistic data. Likewise, McEnery & Hardie (2012, p. 2) assert that corpus linguistics is not a branch of linguistics but a methodology, rather than an aspect of language requiring description or explanation. However, corpus linguistics has undergone a transformation in its nature, transitioning from being a peripheral element of linguistics to an essential component and method thereof. Since the 1990s, corpus linguistics has begun to emerge distinctly from other linguistic fields and a certain number of adherents to Firth's doctrines (1957, p. 32) seek to regard it as a distinct domain within linguistics.

Many linguists argue that this discipline encompasses aspects that go beyond mere methodological roles. This domain encompasses all activities related to data collection, a factor that is leading to an exponential change in our understanding of language (Halliday & James, 1993, p. 24). Other experts justify this as being also due to the use of computing and various statistical and algorithmic methods, tools that have brought about a qualitative change in terms of data extraction and examination. In the 21st century, we can assert that corpus linguistics has evolved into a new field of research and a new philosophical approach to linguistic studies. According to Cabré (1999, p. 25), the famous quote from Saussure, "It is the point of view that creates the object," can aid in explaining this shift in methodological focus. If the dimensions of the point of view change, the object created is substantially different from the previous one. Therefore, it is the methodology that defines the domain. Consequently, one can argue that corpus linguistics is much more than a methodological foundation for study that is inherently linked to this approach. In this way, corpus linguistics becomes a discipline in its own right, encompassing a clearly specified domain (Tognini-Bonelli, 2001, p. 49). Despite belonging to the sphere of applied linguistics, corpus linguistics now has the capacity to be defined by its own set of rules and elements of knowledge. Consequently, it possesses a specific theoretical status and, as a result, is able to contribute to other disciplines in a specific manner.

In other words, corpus linguistics can be seen as "a theoretical approach with which to study language" (Teubert, 2005, p. 2). On the other hand, other authors believe that the corpus is nothing more than data (corpus-as-method). These authors consider it misguided to argue that data, by themselves, constitute theory. For them, data are data, and theory is theory. Observation and study of data and examples are important for verifying facts and results, but they do not in themselves constitute an exposition or definition (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, pp. 147-78).

2.3.1 Corpora

The surge experienced by corpus linguistics has led to the reformulation of the fundamental criteria guiding corpus compilers in their work. This is because there is more frequent questioning of what constitutes a corpus or what are the indispensable requirements for its creation (Bowker & Pearson, 2002, p. 45). We can define a corpus as a collection of texts –written, spoken, or transcribed– whose quantity and content are considered representative of a particular language for the purpose of conducting various linguistic analyses (Tognini-Bonelli, 2001, p. 53). Another definition could be the study of language based on examples of its usage in real life (McEnery & Wilson, 1996, p. 1). Leech adds to this definition that the linguistic data we use must be authentic –naturally occurring– to serve as the basis for linguistic research. Furthermore, he argues that since the 1960s, the term corpus has been used to define a body of linguistic material in electronic format, capable of being processed by a computer for a specific purpose (1992, p. 106). As for the different parameters and criteria when choosing texts, they will depend on many factors, among which we highlight the typology and the study to be undertaken. However, we can affirm that above all, a corpus must be composed of natural and authentic language (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, p. 2).

3. Objectives and methodology

The objectives of our research were, firstly, to check the normalization of military terminology in the English language at that time. It was quite evident that the British military terminology included a number of terminological items unfamiliar to U.S. troops. However, a more serious difficulty was caused by the fact that British usage included many terminological units identical to some used by the U.S. Army, but having important differences in meaning (War Department, 1943, p. 1). All these factors made us conduct military terminological research taking into consideration the differences –both, at linguistic and at conceptual levels– of the main variations of the English language. The second purpose of our work was to analyze the evolution of military terminology after more than five years of struggle. The evolution of military terminology and the creation of new concepts have not been so far studied. Furthermore, many terminological units that appeared during World War Two are widely used today and we consider this fact to be an important aspect of language meriting a wider study.

The starting point of our task was to select a compilation of terminology written during the time span subjected to study. The U.S. War Department published a military glossary in 1943, titled *British Military Terminology*. It was a small work intended to solve the problems arising from the use of different terminological units between the English-speaking allies during World War Two. As the war went on, the use of the terminology became more and more complex. Due to this, the U.S. War Department edited, on 18 January 1944, the *Dictionary of United Army Terms*, a glossary that contained approximately 7,000 terminological units, abbreviations included. That work can be considered the first relevant compilation of military terminology in the English language made in the Twentieth Century and it was used as the starting point of our study.

Our methodology was three-fold. Considering we had two glossaries to check the terminological items, our task was to confirm or reject their validity contrasting the use of the military terminology at that time. On one hand, we carried out an up-to-date terminology extraction compilation using a term extraction software: SDL MultiTerm 2009 Extract. Once finished, we analyzed the

candidate terms identified by the program. After the elimination of the lexical units mistakenly considered as terminological ones, we selected the list of candidate terms which was to be used as the core of our glossary.

On the other hand, we also carried out a term identification process by means of a corpus linguistics tool –AntConc 3.5.9 (Windows) 2020. This second phase was divided into two steps: the first one was made to explore the raw corpus and to analyze the terms in context. One peculiarity of specialized texts is the abundance of terminological units in them. The co-occurrence of terminological items is key to identify multi-word terms, as well as to find closely related terminological units and their definitions in context. Likewise, in this stage, we studied carefully those term candidates extracted from SDL MultiTerm 2009 Extract that we have never heard of. The following step was to use the tagged corpus in order to study the grammatical patterns employed to create multi-lexical terminological units.

The aim of the third phase was to verify if new technologies were so reliable and accurate so as to confirm the futility of text reading. Fortunately, the corpus analysis tool helps us identify the candidate terms in context, the number of times they appeared in our corpus and –on many occasions– their definition. Likewise, it is not sufficient to rely on a term extraction tool if a researcher does not know what he/she expects to find. The excessive amount of *noise* created by SDL MultiTerm 2009 Extract –id est, lexical items erroneously extracted from the software and considered by it as terminological units (Cabre et al., 2001, p. 56)– made the task of searching new terms rather difficult, and a very challenging one if we expected to discover terminological items not considered as such.

3.1 Building up a corpus

The initial stage of our study was the selection of texts to compile a corpus suitable to our needs. Centered on analyzing the *real use* of military terminological items during a specific time frame, it was logical to look for texts written at that time for obvious reasons. The question arose about the availability of specialized texts that may include the terminological units we wanted to scrutinize. We did not simply want to choose texts written at that time because, in our opinion, “the bigger a corpus is not the better” (McEnery, 2013, p. 2); we looked for texts of quality which helped us in our research. A smaller and well-defined corpus is much more useful, compared to a bigger one that does not fit our needs (Bowker & Pearson, 2002, p. 48). Besides, we were looking for terminological items, not lexical ones, which implied more exhaustive research as regards of texts to be selected.

Due to the scarcity of relevant written works, we decided to use some manuals and periodicals published by the U.S. War Department. For that reason, we chose thirty-eight issues of the *Intelligence Bulletin* –a periodical issued between September, 1942 and June, 1946, and printed by the Military Intelligence Service–; a handbook on German military forces, published in March, 1945; a *Field Manual*, dealing with camouflage of vehicles, written by members of the Corps of Engineers –dated on April 2, 1944–; thirteen issues of *The Field Artillery Journal* –edited by the United States Field Artillery Association between September, 1939 and December, 1944–; and forty-two issues of *Tactical and Technical Trends* –printed between June 18, 1942, and June 1,

1944, by the Military Intelligence Service. With all these texts we built up a corpus of ninety-eight texts that contained 2,160,147 words; a rather small but highly specialized one.

One important aspect to point out is the problem of availability of written relevant sources. Sometimes it is quite difficult to look for the information required and so we had to make use of the information we had within reach. It would have been extremely positive to have texts edited by the British Royal Army or by the U.S. Marine Corps, and all the U.S. Army arms and services. It would have also been warmly welcomed the use of written information related to the naval forces. However, due to the scarcity of specialized texts, we had to modify our objectives and to rescind our initial goals. For these reasons, our task was mainly focused on the American variation of the English language and on ground and air forces. Nevertheless, the glossary we used as the main reference also pointed out the lack of terminological units of the naval armed forces and that many of them were used both, by military and civilian navies (War Department, 1944).

The second phase of the preparation of our source of information was the creation of making two corpora: a raw corpus, and a grammatically tagged one. As previously stated, the first corpus was initially used for the term extraction by means of the SDL MultiTerm 2009 Extract software. The second corpus was the previous one but tagged using the CLAWS7 –the Constituent Likelihood Automatic Word-tagging System– tagset, developed by UCREL, at Lancaster University. Likewise, we have previously mentioned that the raw corpus was also used to identify terminological items –its evolution, variation, and the new ones which were not found in previous glossaries–, a task we continued with the aid of the already described corpus analysis tool. This was also the program chosen to carry out the part-of-speech tagging process in a subsequent phase.

3.2 Term extraction

We will proceed to describe the term extraction process carried out with SDL MultiTerm 2009 Extract. We set the extraction process as a monolingual one in American English, using a file of excluded terms –i.e., a file that includes a basic vocabulary of English, used to decrease the amount of *noise*. We also created a file to store the discarded terms for a future analysis. Likewise, we used a stopword list, letting that a term could be made from one to four words, not providing a minimum figure of terms extracted, and placing the *silence/noise* ratio at 50 percent.

The resulting term candidate list amounted to 13,294 and contained a high degree of lexical units that were clearly identified and, consequently, deleted. One aspect to mention –as regards to the *noise* problem– is the search for multi-lexical terminological units. The higher the number of words a term may be composed of, the higher the percentage of *noise* will be found. In any case, we have preferred to exercise a closer look at these complex terminological items, despite the awareness that the elimination of multi-lexical units was going to be a tedious task. Another aspect worth mentioning is the inclusion of numerous foreign words. The program simply interpreted that these words were not common in English as language for general purposes and, automatically, labeled them as candidate terms. It is a defect that we will find in every historical military terminological research, provided that there will be a high figure of foreign candidate terms that will deserve further analysis. However, it will also imply a high percentage of *noise* –for example, military ranks written in other languages, which are not relevant to our research and subsequently deleted.

During the elimination of the lexical items extracted erroneously by the software, a context sentence was added to those candidate terms which needed a thorough examination in order to analyze them in context. SDL MultiTerm 2009 Extract permits us to extract context sentences, allowing us to select up to a figure of ten to carry out this analysis. However, the ones used in the glossary were finally selected using AntConc 3.5.9 (Windows) 2020 for reasons of ease. On many occasions, it was needed to use this program to define whether a candidate term was finally included in our terminological glossary, as we were able to review all the content sentences a candidate term appeared and –in many circumstances– discovered its definition as well. In sum, we considered it more adequate to use this corpus linguistics analysis tool to choose a context sentence that could conveniently represent the conceptological item it described.

4. Analysis of the results

The findings of this research illuminate the rich tapestry of military terminology during World War Two, revealing a dynamic landscape characterized by innovation, adaptation, and cultural exchange. Terminological records offer a window into the evolving nature of warfare, from the intricacies of artillery deployment to the nuances of tactical maneuvering. Synonymy emerges as a prevalent phenomenon, underscoring the fluidity of language and the diverse linguistic influences shaping military discourse. Moreover, the incorporation of foreign terms and their translations underscores the interconnectedness of global conflict, highlighting the role of language as a conduit for cross-cultural exchange and strategic collaboration.

Up to now, in this research, we have identified 4,496 terminological items –all of them found in the corpus. However, regarding their definitions, we had not only to rely on wartime glossaries but on other sources detailed below:

Wartime glossaries:	2,717 definitions
Post-war-glossaries:	50 definitions
Online dictionaries:	271 definitions
Online encyclopedia:	175 definitions
Source texts:	281 definitions
Author's proposal:	150 definitions
Synonyms, abbreviations and acronyms:	852 definitions

Terminological records reveal the complexity and richness of military discourse during World War Two, with examples ranging from familiar terms like *soldier* to specialized concepts such as *envelopment* –53 hits. Synonymy is prevalent, evidenced by variations like *enveloping attack* –5 hits–, *enveloping movement* –8 hits–, *enveloping operation* –1 hit– and *Umfassungsangriff*, the German translation equivalent –1 hit. However, on some occasions, conceptological units have been narrowed, providing the need to denote a slight variation in meaning with the apparition of new terminological units, as it occurs with *double envelopment* –10 hits–, *vertical envelopment* –5 hits– and *flan(king) envelopment* –4 hits. Not all of these terms were included in wartime glossaries; those that were not were found in the corpus –as well as their definitions–, confirming the dramatic evolution in warfare at a pace difficult to normalize at terminological level during wartime.

On the other hand, synonymy ranges from the different use of terminological units in initial uppercase or lowercase –*Aide-de-Camp* vs. *aide-de-camp*– to the transformation of monolexical terms to plurilexical ones or even with the addition of a slash between them –e.g., *frontline*, *front line* and *front-line*. As stated earlier, some of the synonyms were recorded in the two glossaries printed during the war; however, the majority were not. Besides, there exists a high proportion of synonyms used in the military jargon, mainly by non-commissioned officers and soldiers, to ease the understanding of the concepts dealt with. For this reason, the use of synonyms was abundant. Taking *submachine gun*, as an example, ten synonyms have been identified –*hand weapon* (5 hits), *machine carbine* (18 hits), *machine pistol* (83 hits), *M.P.* (16 hits), *SMG* (1 hit), *sub-machine gun* (11 hits), *submachine-gun* (3 hits), *Sub-MG* (2 hits), *Tommy gun* (58 hits) and *zipper gun* (1 hit)–, despite it is not a term difficult to understand. Another example of this evolution can also be observed in *sandbag* –*sand bag* (32 hits) and *sand-bag* (5 hits)–, although, in this case, the use of the terminological unit has been broadened. In general, terms are used as nouns; however, on this occasion, we have discovered that it was also used as an adjective and as a verb –*sandbagged* (3 hits) and *sandbagging* (1 hit).

The unrecorded terminological items discovered in the corpus are the enlightening part of the research. Regarding those whose definitions were found in the corpus or those to which we proposed a definition, we can highlight *additional armor* –14 hits–, *alarm cartridge* –9 hits–, *antitank artillery* –21 hits–, *ball mount* –10 hits–, *dazzle* –28 hits–, *demolition party* –20 hits–, *double-truss*, *single-story bridge* –1 hit–, *dummy aircraft* –3 hits–, *Motpulk* –8 hits–, *rocket system* –1 hit– and *sliding mine* –6 hits–, among others. An important percentage of these new terminological items will be normalized and included in future glossaries, while others –as they ceased to be employed– will be obliterated.

The corpus also highlights the incorporation of foreign terminology within the U.S. Army, with 105 German terms –*blitz*, *bunker*, *Flak*, *jäger*, *kampfgruppe*, *panzer*, *panzer grenadier*, *Stuka*, *U-boat*, etc.–, permeating military discourse. Besides, many of these German terminological units became part of the English general lexicon as their meanings became familiar to the general public due to the lexicalization process (Brinton & Traugott, 2005). On the other hand, a comparison of British English and American English terminologies underscores linguistic variations and nuances between the two dialects. We have analyzed 86 British English terms in the corpus and identified that some of them are different to those used within the U.S. Army to denote the same conceptological unit. An example of these variations can be seen below:

BRITISH ENGLISH

advanced dressing station (3 hits)

car post (1 hit)

delivery point (4 hits)

pin-point target (4 hits)

reconnaissance aircraft (12 hits)

forward observation officer/FOO/F.O.O. (27 hits)

AMERICAN ENGLISH

collection station (2 hits)

ambulance loading post (2 hits)

distribution point (6 hits)

precision fire (8 hits)

observation aviation (1 hit)

no equivalent

As stated earlier, this is an ongoing process and, in this paper, we aimed at highlighting –in general terms– the findings and results obtained insofar.

5. Conclusions

The evolution of military terminology during World War Two stands as a testament to the enduring importance of linguistic precision in warfare. Beyond mere semantics, the standardization and evolution of military language served as a cornerstone for effective communication, strategic planning and operational coordination. As we reflect upon the legacy of this pivotal period in military history, it becomes clear that the study of terminology holds profound implications for our understanding of past conflicts and informs contemporary debates surrounding defense policy and strategic doctrine. Terminology management is a lengthy and costly process (Schmitz, 2009, p. 18) and terminological standardization is needed in every discipline (Sager, 1990). Nevertheless, by unraveling the complexities of military discourse, we gain invaluable insights into the nature of warfare, the dynamics of intercultural exchange, and the enduring power of language to shape human endeavors. It goes without saying that standardization of military terminology took place at the end of hostilities, where new lexical representations denoting new advances were added to the glossaries. However, not all were included. As stated earlier, those concepts that brought about improvisation or were no longer implemented –for different reasons– were excluded.

Regarding synonymy, we observed –overall– 911 examples and this is the main concern of all the parties, as it leads to confusion, a fact to be avoided. Univocity in specialised discourse is key and, despite the use of synonyms and paraphrasing is advisable to be used on instances for the sake of better comprehension –in particular, in a communication between expert-non experts or officers-soldiers– it may jeopardize specialised communication

Finally, another aspect worth mentioning is the lexicalization or de-terminologization process (Meyer & Mackintosh, 2000), where many military terminological units are so widely used among the general public –*camouflage* is a clear example– that are nowadays included in English dictionaries. This is a matter that will be subjected to study in future works.

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